

Why Understanding Pore Pressure Matters in Oil and Gas Exploration and Safe Well Delivery: A Review

Pratap V. Nair¹ and Anjanava D. Purkayastha²

¹ Retired Exploration Petroleum Geologist, Devidarshan, Kawdiar, Thiruvananthapuram - 695003, Kerala, India;

² Pore Pressure Specialist and Data Science Researcher in Pore Pressure Prediction

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJETED-69342D9E61AA9

Published: 2025-12-07

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845988>

Page No: 121-137

ABSTRACT

Lithology and principal stress are the main factors affecting the development of the subsurface pore pressure profile. Lithology affects geological compartmentalisation. Identifying paleoenvironment and sediment distribution is key to understanding pressure systems. While most basins are mature regarding shallow prospectivity, they remain immature for deeper plays. The lack of deep calibration data makes pressure prediction difficult. The importance of pore pressure prediction cannot be overstated, as errors can be costly during drilling, and the worst-case scenario is adverse social impact. Knowing pore pressure has become increasingly crucial for drilling in depleted, deep, or overpressured zones. Understanding geological processes is essential for evaluating the preservation and dissipation of pore pressure. Pore pressure is a vital factor in geology and petroleum systems. A thorough understanding of this parameter helps predict drilling hazards, evaluate reservoirs, and ensure safe hydrocarbon exploration. The main control on overpressure distribution is the relationship between permeable and impermeable facies. Identifying low-permeability seals is vital in petroleum exploration, considering both prospectivity and drilling safety. Understanding the occurrence of reservoir facies, their associated pressure regimes, and their precise stratigraphic positions enhances comprehension of top-seal integrity and prospectivity, making the model more dependable. The paper emphasises that estimating pressure magnitude is essential for well planning to enable smooth operations and minimise risk during drilling. The social impact of pore-pressure prediction is significant, and derisking is necessary.

Keywords: Pore pressure prediction, seismic, drilling, basin modelling, and uncertainty.

Cite This Paper: PRATAP V NAIR AND ANJANAVA D. PURKAYASTHA (2025). "Why Understanding Pore Pressure Matters in Oil and Gas Exploration and Safe Well Delivery: A Review". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ENGINEERING AND DEVELOPMENT (IJETED)*, vol. 15, no. 6, 2025, pp. 121-137. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845988>

Corresponding Author: Pratap V Nair ✉ vpratapnair@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Understanding pore pressure is a crucial aspect of prospect generation—drilling planning, well design, subsurface evaluation, and the safe execution of wells. For many geoscientists and drilling engineers, predicting pore pressure goes beyond simple theoretical analysis—it is a vital process that greatly influences safety, operational costs, and decision-making. A single

calculation error can lead to severe consequences, such as wellbore instability, kicks, stuck pipe, or even a total blowout, as in the Macondo disaster of 2010 in the Gulf of Mexico (Figure 1). The catastrophic blowout of the Macondo well, also known as the Deepwater Horizon incident, serves as a stark reminder of the critical importance of pore-pressure prediction in oil and gas operations. This tragic event was caused by the failure to accurately forecast and manage elevated pore pressure, resulting in a blowout that led to the rig's explosion, the sad loss of 11 lives, and the release of millions of barrels of oil into the Gulf of Mexico¹.

Figure 1: Macondo catastrophe in the Gulf of Mexico in 2010¹

Consequently, the ability to predict pore pressure has become a key element of modern drilling practices in the upstream oil and gas sector. The industry faces the challenge that when focus is placed on commercial risk, technical and safety risks are often overlooked. We emphasise the need for a balance between safety and commercial risks at all times during exploration drilling. The devastating impact of the Macondo blowout incident has underscored the importance of informed decisions based on technical confidence for successful drilling and completion operations, particularly in deep offshore environments.

Predicting pore pressure is crucial when drilling in deep, geologically complex reservoirs. Even in hydrocarbon reservoirs that are relatively well-characterised and have numerous wells drilled, challenging geological conditions can lead to inaccurate predictions of abnormal pore pressure. Such inaccuracies may cause catastrophic incidents, risking human lives and infrastructure.

We strive to compile the current state of pore pressure prediction and identify the need to develop additional techniques to address the challenges, ensuring that the adverse effects on both the exploring company and society are minimised in this domain, which is plagued by inherent uncertainty. Mastering pore pressure prediction has become crucial in oil and gas exploration, particularly as deeper, high-pressure, high-temperature environments and ultra-deep water have become commonplace. Additionally, exploration expenses escalate significantly in these ventures, prompting companies to exert every effort to manage costs effectively.

Why technically pore pressure matters

Pore pressure is the pressure that fluids exert within the pore spaces of geological formations. Subsurface overpressure profiles are greatly affected by lithology and principal stresses. Vertical stress results from the combined weight of sediment and water. The water depth in offshore regions directly influences the size of the regional hydrostatic-lithostatic pressure envelope. Evaluating hydrocarbon prospects with an emphasis on top seals is a wise approach, especially given the high costs of exploration drilling. When drilling, it is crucial to design the well properly to ensure the mud weight adequately counteracts the pressure. Too little mud weight can cause kicks, whereas too much can fracture the formation. Achieving this balance requires a thorough understanding of the subsurface stress conditions, starting with an accurate estimate of pore pressure before and during drilling.

In the current industry landscape, predicting pore pressure is not limited to deepwater or high-pressure wells. Even in onshore environments with seemingly straightforward geology, pressure anomalies can go unnoticed and sometimes, the effect of hydrocarbon column inflation occurs. These anomalies often result from rapid sedimentation, undercompaction, fluid expansion, tectonic compression, or hydrocarbon generation. Identifying the geological factors that lead to pressure retention is the first step in any pore pressure prediction process to develop a reliable predictive model.

Prediction Techniques in Vogue

Pore pressure prediction spans a broad range of disciplines across the upstream oil and gas industry, so it requires collaboration among geology, geophysics, petrophysics, geomechanics, drilling operations, and drilling engineering. Pore pressure can be estimated through different datasets and models. Most often, the datasets are pervasive across disciplines. Over-pressured formations exhibit several of the following properties when compared with a normally pressured section at the same depth^{III}: (1) higher porosities, (2) lower bulk densities, (3) lower effective stresses, (4) higher temperatures, (5) lower interval velocities, (6) higher Poisson's ratios. The most commonly used techniques fall into five categories: seismic-based, log-based, drilling-based, basin modelling and upcoming approaches.

1. Seismic-Based Prediction

Seismic velocities exhibit a significant relationship with porosity and compaction in mudrocks. In undercompacted shales, reduced velocities typically signify elevated pore pressure. For sediments to undergo compaction, pore water must be expelled (Figure 1). However, if sedimentation occurs rapidly relative to the time required for fluid to be expelled from the pore space, or if seals inhibit dewatering and compaction during burial, the pore fluid may become overpressured, thereby supporting a portion of the overburden.

Figure 1: Disequilibrium compaction model

Pore pressure can be estimated from seismic velocities using a velocity-to-pore-pressure transformation calibrated against offset wells.^{IV} By constructing an interval-velocity model and juxtaposing it with a standard compaction trend, geoscientists can predict in-situ pore pressure prior to drilling. This approach is especially beneficial in frontier basins or deepwater settings where pre-drill planning is crucial.

2. Log-Based Techniques

Once drilling is underway, log data provides a more accurate picture. There could be logging while or after drilling. Transport (Resistivity and acoustic) and bulk (density) properties of mudrocks are related to porosity, and drilling into overpressured rocks would increase porosity (Figure 2). This can be applied in real time(real-time pore pressure prediction, Figure 3).

Figure 2: Response of transport and bulk properties to overpressure

Figure 3: An example of real-time pore pressure prediction

These methods enable the monitoring team to refine predictions made during the pre-drill stage, update the pressure profile as more data becomes available, and advise the drilling team accordingly in real time. For rocks undergoing compaction, porosity and vertical effective stress are correlated in mudrocks. Some logs are highly correlated with porosity, namely sonic, resistivity, and density logs. They can be transformed into vertical effective stress and, in turn, into estimates of pore pressure. The accuracy and uncertainty depend on the calibration data range.

The sonic transform used for pore pressure prediction can be applied to seismic-velocity-based predictions after the seismic velocity is conditioned to the wellbore sonic velocity. seismic velocities are often different from velocities measured in boreholes. Vertical seismic profiling may be carried out in key wells, and based on the transform ahead of the bit, pore pressure predictions may be confirmed. The interval velocity from seismic reflection data is the velocity parallel to the bedding plane, while the sonic velocity is the velocity perpendicular to the bedding plane. Anisotropy effects depend on rock properties and may influence both well logs and seismic velocity. The purpose of seismic-to-well calibration is to account for these factors by applying a scaling factor that improves the representation of accurate subsurface velocities in seismic data.

3. Drilling-Based Indicators and Real-time pore predictions

Real-time drilling parameters act as the final layer of confirmation. Changes in penetration rate, pit gain, shale density, cuttings shape and volume, or mud gas readings provide immediate clues about unexpected pressure zones (Figure 4). Well flow, the gain in the mud pit due to well influx, and kicks typically serve as direct indicators of pore pressure exceeding the mud weight within the well. Because these indicators respond instantly to changes in formation, they are a critical component of operational safety. Some appear immediately during drilling, whereas others, such as mud gas and cuttings, exhibit a lag time before their appearance. This is part of real-time pore pressure prediction.

The pressure indicators in the drilling assembly indicate whether underbalanced drilling is occurring, a key technique for real-time pore pressure detection. During drilling, data on downhole mud weight (either Equivalent Circulating Density, ECD or Equivalent Static Density, ESD) can be acquired. The status of overbalance or underbalance can be determined by comparing the predicted pore pressure gradient with the downhole mud weight. Mud gas, when correctly interpreted, is a vital indicator of pore pressure in oil well drilling (Figure 5). Along with Logging while Drilling, which allows log-based pore pressure prediction, drilling-based indicators are used to calibrate these predictions.

Figure 4: Drilling based indicators

Figure 5: Mud gas indications of overpressure

4. Basin Modelling

The evolution of pressure and temperature controls many subsurface processes. In a basin model, both are coupled at each time step. A basin model will generate overpressure through fluid flow, either by retaining fluid or by moving it. Fluid flow in a basin model is controlled

by the distribution of permeable to impermeable units. Compaction trends as a function of stress are assigned to each lithology in the basin model to simulate the evolution of porosity and permeability, which control fluid flow through the basin. Basin Modelling verifies the geological model and enables predictions across the basin (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Basin Modelling for pore pressure prediction

5. Machine Learning Applications and State of the art technologies

Machine Learning algorithms are increasingly helping identify subtle pressure trends that conventional analysis techniques can be missed in complex geological environments.^V This is in the incipient stage. Three-dimensional geomechanical modelling and real-time data analysis are transforming the way geoscientists address subsurface uncertainty.

Challenges in Pore pressure prediction

Despite the wide range of sophisticated predictive tools available, predicting pore pressure remains challenging. Pore pressure prediction is not a cookbook workflow activity. In all cases, a good geological framework is required to understand the distribution and magnitudes of overpressure. This becomes particularly critical when drilling wildcat wells, as greenfield pore-pressure prediction is rife with geological challenges, and geological complexities may not have been fully understood at the start. In many basins, tectonic forces alter the normal compaction trend, making traditional models less reliable. Overpressure generated by fluid expansion or hydrocarbon maturation may not show clear seismic or log signatures. Precise analysis of pore pressure relies on identifying and calibrating the relationship between effective stress and porosity, utilising thermal and chemical processes that modify porosity.

1. Uncertainty associated with seismic velocities

The commonly used techniques have their own challenges. The uncertainty associated with seismic velocities is due to data quality and processing. Seismic data is affected by acquisition parameters, processing techniques, and structural distortions and may not be geologically

consistent. Velocity picking is in itself a challenge. Building a high-confidence velocity model requires careful calibration with nearby wells, which may not always be available. Seismic velocities are not a perfect description of the subsurface velocities due to:

- Errors in RMS velocity picking – Interpretation.
- Assumptions are made to convert RMS to interval velocities (e.g. Dix).
- Anisotropy: Seismic velocity is horizontal; well velocities are vertical.

Velocity analysis needs to be integrated with geologic model(s) and well data to provide more robust predictions and better uncertainty assessment. Historically, workflows have focused on young clastic basins in extensional settings with simple burial histories. However, many issues could persist.

2. Comprehension of the geological environment

Understanding the geological environment is crucial; without it, accurate predictions are impossible. This is because understanding the distribution of lithological facies is necessary to grasp how permeability varies over time and space, as it does today. Regardless of the cause, the magnitude and distribution of observed overpressures will depend primarily on the arrangement of high- and low-permeability zones within the subsurface. The anticipated pore pressure profile from the shelf to the sea is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – A conceptual diagram illustrating the variation in subsurface pore pressure profiles as lithofacies change along a cross-section that extends from shelf to bathyal environments; MFS = maximum flooding surface^{VI}

Consequently, undercompacted intervals will continue to follow the standard compaction path; however, the rocks in this state will exhibit greater porosity and lower velocity than normally compacted rocks at the same burial depth. When the formation temperature exceeds 100°C, the normal compaction trend (NCT) is altered. This marks the point of maximum vertical effective stress in the region's geological history. When unloading pressure mechanisms occur, the increase in pore pressure halts compaction, and both porosity and density stop altering with

increasing burial depth. As fluid pressure rises and effective stress decreases, the rock cannot increase its porosity, as compaction is irreversible. Therefore, the grain contact area remains essentially unchanged. Nonetheless, an increase in pore pressure reduces grain contact stress, thereby decreasing velocity. Such cases should be identified at the pre-drill stage to prevent surprises during drilling.

This results in the typical unloading signature, as shown in Figure 8 in the deeper section, where the density log ceases to change, and the sonic log reverses abruptly.^{VII} This phenomenon can be easily recognised by cross-plotting sonic and density logs for a specific well, as illustrated in Figure 9.^{VIII} In these plots, the unloaded zone is distinctly identified because the velocity-density plot exhibits a sharp transition: the velocity drops while the density remains constant. Failing to recognise this change in the region will lead to an overestimation of vertical effective stress. Therefore, understanding the mechanism that causes overpressure is essential.

Figure 8 Velocity and density logs showing the physical properties of normally compacting rocks (blue trend lines), undercompacted rocks (orange trend lines), and unloading (red trend lines).^{VII}

Figure 9: Velocity-density Crossplot illustrating evolutionary pathways with increasing VES.^{VIII}

3. Uncertainty associated with shale picking

Pore-pressure prediction is based on models relating porosity to vertical effective stress, which requires selecting the same type of shale from well logs.^{IX} The fundamental workflow for pore pressure prediction involves constructing a model from pre-drill offset data and applying it during drilling while monitoring the well in real time. Accurate shale selection at both stages is crucial for converting log data into pore pressures; however, inconsistencies in the approach to identifying shale points during model building and real-time monitoring, as well as discrepancies among different predictors, can lead to incorrect pore pressure estimates, even with lithological influences on the tool. Some workers refer to this shale selection as a normal compaction trend (NCT). In the workflow of 3D Pore Pressure Modelling, it is essential to establish an appropriate NCT, which necessitates a high degree of human interpretation and geological insight.^X Failure to establish it correctly may lead to significant uncertainty in the ultimate prediction of pore pressure. Therefore, an optimised shale selection strategy integrated with well behaviour is essential for predicting pore pressures within realistic uncertainty limits and preventing both under- and over-prediction.

4. Pressure prediction while drilling:

Limits on the Accuracy of Pore Pressure Estimates; Uncertainty inherent in downhole logging tools; Information derived from mud weights, mineralogy, gas data, and density analysis of sample cuttings can improve (lower) uncertainty. Because uncertainty is due to instrumentation, no improvement is possible without measurement refinement or additional data. Effective communication, by conveying pore pressure estimates to the drilling crew on time, is mandatory to avoid incidents. No universal standards or protocols appear to exist in this key area, and it would be advisable for oil majors to share their approaches to working together.

Error Propagation in Multiple Data Sources:

Depth, hydrostatic fluid density, overburden gradient, trend setting, and log measurements have uncertainties. Without instrumentation refinement, combine estimates with unrelated measurements to reduce uncertainty and trim error bars. Logging tools and surface laboratory measurements depend on their design and the physics involved. The uncertainty in density and sonic tools affects calculations of overburden and pore pressure gradients, limiting the uncertainty in pore pressure gradients to ± 0.5 ppg and in fracture gradients to ± 0.6 ppg. Improved tools or additional measurements are needed to reduce uncertainty.^{XI}

We want to draw a parallel between error propagation in pore-pressure prediction and the Swiss cheese model of accident causation. The Swiss cheese model of accident causation illustrates that, although many layers of defence lie between hazards and accidents, flaws in each layer can, if aligned, allow an accident to occur. In Figure 10, three hazard vectors are stopped by the defences, but one passes through where the "holes" are lined up.^{XII}

Figure 10: Swiss cheese model^{XII}

Experience shows that pore pressure calculations are always uncertain unless improved instruments are used. Fracture gradient and wellbore stability calculations also face similar uncertainties. Future analytical breakthroughs are possible, but reducing random error through measurement validation is achievable now through meticulous well event monitoring and combining various drilling events.

5. Challenges due to complex geology

The industry faces challenges due to complex geology. The summary of challenges includes;

- Prediction in carbonates
- Consistent rock properties from basin modelling to velocity-based prediction (+QI, inversion, 4D and so on)
- Prediction in complex geological settings:
 - Tectonic settings
 - Subsalt
 - Complex stress histories
 - Complex lithologies
 - Older and more compacted or lithified or diagenetically altered rocks, including many unconventional plays.
- Distinguishing the pressure signal from lithology

Why is the Knowledge of Mechanism Important?

- The mechanism influences the timing of geopressuring and the stress history of the area.
- Differing mechanisms impact rock properties in different ways (e.g. porosity/permeability evolution during compaction behaviour, acoustic properties).

- Some mechanisms are more likely to cause pressure disequilibrium between mudrocks and sands.
- Some mechanisms can be modelled with velocities and/or basin modelling, some cannot (easily).
- The origin of the overpressure must be understood in relation to the pressure-generating mechanism. This determines the vertical effective stress, and only the unloading mechanism would produce a low VES environment alongside a velocity rebound (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Effect of pressure-generating mechanism on VES estimation

Operational factors also add to uncertainty. For instance, errors in mud weight measurements, poor hole cleaning, or inconsistent logging quality can distort the pressure model. Since pore pressure prediction involves combining data from various disciplines, miscommunication between teams can also cause misinterpretation. A good understanding of pore pressure prediction is fundamental to de-risking exploration ventures, as it helps prevent unforeseen issues.

Impact of Pore Pressure Prediction in Oil and Gas Exploration

Both from the prospect ranking and drilling perspectives, it is critical to define the overpressure system clearly. Pressure prediction is essential for several reasons throughout the exploration process. Broadly, the impact of pore pressure prediction can be classified into two categories.

1. Prospect Generation
2. Drilling Safety

Prospect Generation

The failure of a laterally continuous seal can occur when fluids exceed either the capillary entry pressure or the seal's mechanical strength.^{XIII} Pore pressure plays a crucial role in evaluating

prospects in three main ways. First, mechanical top-seal failure can occur at low vertical effective stress (VES), indicating that a safe trap is necessary for success (Figure 11).^{XIV} Second, overpressure helps maintain reservoir porosity. Third, there are costs involved in drilling high-pressure traps. Mechanical seal failure can occur when pore pressure exceeds the fracturing pressure, thereby restricting the hydrocarbon column. Research shows that many traps with low retention capacities were dry, especially in areas with high overpressure. Gaarenstroom et al. (1993)^{XV} indicated that in the central North Sea, most traps with retention capacities below 800 psi were dry.

To retain hydrocarbons, a "protected trap" is crucial, especially in areas with high overpressure. The requirement of a laterally extensive reservoir to house the charge is fundamental. The effect on the pore pressure profile is to reduce overpressure when sand occurs. However, if only thin and isolated discontinuous sands are present, overpressures will remain high. Reservoirs and pore pressures must be consistent with the net-to-gross ratio. For example, in the Gulf of Mexico, some traps are destroyed while others remain protected, allowing hydrocarbon accumulation. The maximum VES affects rock compaction, which in turn influences reservoir porosity predictions. A balance exists where low VES benefits porosity, but if VES is too low, the seal may fail. Maps can be created to identify regions with both high porosity and low risk of seal failure. It is important to remember that the maximum VES has the most significant impact on reservoir porosity. If the historical VES was lower than it is now, current porosity measurements might not be accurate. Additionally, geological history significantly influences seal failure, as past leaks at low VES may not be relevant to current conditions. In 1992, Tennant demonstrated the locations of traps in pressure communication with shallower leak points, which have aquifer pressures equivalent to the top seal fracture pressure. These traps are protected against mechanical failure of the top seal by adjusting the fluid pressure based on the shallow top seal leak pressure.^{XVI}

Pore pressure prediction should also be considered when conducting a risk and volumetric assessment of a given prospect. In an overpressured system, there is a risk that high pressures may breach the top seal. This may lead to a reduced hydrocarbon column (impacting the volumetrics) or, at worst, a completely blown trap. Understanding pore pressure is, therefore, a key part of successful exploration.

Figure 11: Top seal integrity and hydrocarbon accumulation^{XIV}

Drilling Safety

The accurate prediction of pore pressure is a crucial factor in well design. Overestimating pore pressure can cause drilling mud to invade the formation and damage it, leading to over-engineering of the well and unnecessary extra costs. Conversely, underestimating pore pressure may result in premature well abandonment or, in the worst cases, blowouts and major safety incidents. Precise pore pressure prediction directly enhances drilling safety. By anticipating pressure ramps and transition zones, petroleum engineers can plan appropriate casing points, optimise mud weights, and minimise non-productive time. A well-developed pore pressure–fracture gradient (PPFG) model is vital for selecting casing depths that prevent kicks and losses.

Pore pressure and fracture pressure are critical for the design and safe operation of wells. Errors in assessing these pressures can cause dangerous situations, such as blowouts, which may result in fires, leaks, and uncontrolled flow from the ground. Such events can lead to fatalities, injuries, environmental harm, and substantial losses. Damage to facilities and loss of wells are also potential consequences of inaccurate predictions. The most recent reminder of this is the Bagjhan oil well disaster of 2023 in the Tinsukia district of Assam, India (Figure 12).^{XVII}

Figure 12: Bagjhan oil well in Assam's Tinsukia district^{XVII}

Process Safety aims to ensure that wells and drilling equipment are well designed, safely operated, and properly maintained. This requires technical expertise, effective communication, strong leadership, ongoing risk assessment, and continuous improvement of safety measures.

From a business perspective, accurate forecasts reduce the chances of unexpected operational issues. Problems like stuck pipes, sidetracks, or well-control incidents can cost millions of pounds. In high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) wells, both financial and safety risks are significantly greater. This can have a massive impact on operations (exploration and development drilling), both on executing these wells safely and on completing the operations on time and within budget. As a result, pore pressure and geomechanical modelling have become essential parts of risk management strategies across the upstream oil industry.

Look Ahead in Pore Pressure Prediction

The halcyon days of oil exploration seem to be behind us, as successful discoveries become less frequent while exploration ventures into more challenging environments—deeper into HPHT zones and ultra-deep waters such as the Niger Delta, offshore Krishna-Godavari, and others—the importance of accurate pore pressure prediction grows. Oil majors investing in advanced predictive technologies not only improve safety but also enhance efficiency and risk management. The future lies in integrated approaches that combine traditional geoscience with sophisticated data analytics, providing real-time pressure predictions that adapt as new drilling data becomes available. For geoscientists and drilling engineers, mastering pore pressure prediction is no longer just a technical skill; it increasingly determines whether a project succeeds or fails in today's complex exploration landscape. In an environment where drilling safety and operational efficiency are crucial, mastering pore-pressure prediction has become essential—an indispensable skill for geoscientists and engineers involved in subsurface development.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper offers a comprehensive overview of the significance of pore-pressure prediction for identifying protected traps and ensuring safe well drilling and delivery. A thorough understanding of the geological setting is essential for predicting pore pressure, which is vital for well design and choosing suitable mud weights to reduce associated drilling hazards. The primary factor influencing overpressure distribution is the relation between permeable and impermeable facies. It is essential to identify the presence of low-permeability seals in petroleum exploration, balancing the potential for discovery with safety considerations. Pore pressure prediction can be undertaken using several approaches requiring input from multiple technical disciplines. Effective pore pressure work requires strong collaboration and open dialogue among multidisciplinary professionals. While most professionals possess extensive knowledge in geology, geophysics, and drilling engineering, very few, if any, have a comprehensive understanding of all the relevant subject areas.

As the upstream petroleum sector advances into exploring increasingly complex and technically demanding reservoirs, the importance of accurate pore-pressure prediction cannot be overstated. Advances in machine learning, 3D geomechanical modelling, and real-time data analytics are transforming the methods geoscientists and petroleum engineers use to manage subsurface conditions, including pore pressure uncertainty. These developments enable more precise, dynamic prediction models that are continuously refined as new data emerge. It is essential for successful exploration and development. Drilling safety depends heavily on reliable estimates of pore pressure distribution, communicated promptly to the drilling crew, which help control costs and prevent negative social impacts. The consequences of getting these wrong can lead to significant, undesirable events affecting people's safety and the environment. The most dramatic examples of uncontrolled pressure include blowouts, as discussed in the paper. Pushing the limits of exploration requires advancements in pore pressure prediction techniques, both pre-drill and syn-drill. Understanding the pressures is therefore a key part of pursuing a successful exploration campaign.

REFERENCE

I Deepwater Horizon - Macondo Well Blowout

II Shaker, S.S., 2002. Sequence Stratigraphy: Key to Geopressure Profile Assessment, *CSEG Recorder*, V.27. No.7,1-2

III Dutta, N., 2002, Geopressure prediction using seismic data: current status and the road ahead, *Geophysics*, 67, no.6, p 2012-2041.

IV Colin Sayers et al, 2005. Pore pressure in the Gulf of Mexico: Seeing ahead of the bit, *World Oil*, 2005

V Ogbu, A.O., Iwe, K.A., Williams, O., & Ikevuje, A. (2024). Advances in machine learning-driven pore pressure prediction in complex geological settings. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*. 5. 1648-1665. 10.51594/csitrj.v5i7.1350.

VI Anjanava D. Purkayastha and Pratap V. Nair, 2017. Prospect level Normalization of Offset Pore Pressure Measurements: Analysis of Approaches and their Association with Regional Geology SPE-185394-MS

VII Satinder Chopra and Alan Huffman, 2006. Velocity determination for pore pressure prediction 28 CSEG RECORDER April 2006

VIII Swarbrick, R., Lahann, R., and GeoPressure Technology team of Ikon Science in Durham, 2012, "Discussion on Pore pressure-Fracture gradient coupling", SEG-SPE Workshop, Phuket, February 2012, p. 14.

IX D.Purkayastha, Anjanava, Kumar, Mrityunjay, Nair, Pratap, Hansen, Kirk S., and Brent Alan Couzens-Schultz. "Shale Picking Issues and Strategies: Key to Robust Real-Time Model-Based Pore Pressure Prediction." Paper presented at the International Petroleum Technology Conference, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, December 2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2523/IPTC-18029-MS>

X Bhardwaj, Nitin , Gunasekaran, Karthikeyan , Kumar, Ashutosh , and Jayanta Dutta. "Establishment of Appropriate Normal Compaction Trend NCT: A Critical Aspect for Reducing Uncertainty in 3D Pore Pressure Modelling.." Paper presented at the SPE Oil and Gas India Conference and Exhibition, Mumbai, India, April 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/194662-MS>

XI Mark Herkommer, 2017. Limits on the Accuracy of Pore Pressure Estimates by Analysis of Random Measurement Error and Means for Improvement, First EAGE Workshop on Pore Pressure Prediction 19-21 March 2017, Pau, France.

XII [Swiss cheese model - Wikipedia](#)

XIII Summers et al, 2013.Controls on Top seal capacity, *Shell Journal of Technology*, April 2013, p 9-16.

XIV Couzens et al, 2013. Exploration Trap risk, *Shell Exploration Conference*,

XV Gaarenstroom, L., Tromp, R. A. J., de Jong, M. C., Brandenburg, A. M., 1993, Overpressures in the Central North Sea: Implications for trap integrity and drilling safety, In: Parker, J. R., (ed) Petroleum Geology of Northwest Europe: Proceedings of the 4th Conference, Geological Society, London, 1305-1313.

XVI Tennant S.H, 1992. Trapping mechanism, Effective stress, Fluid flow and Velocities in “Hard overpressures Rosita Case study, South Texas, Technical progress report, Shell Bellaire Research Centre, Houston.

XVII [Huge explosion near Baghjan oil well in Assam, 3 foreign experts injured | India News](#)